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Biblical Metaphysics in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: The Role of Pastors in Nigeria

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Abstract

Biblical metaphysics is the understanding of the issue of reality from the biblical point of view. This understanding is the basis for the view anyone may have about every other thing in life; and pastors play important roles in ensuring the understanding. Technological evolution has reached a level where machines are inbuilt with intelligence which was endowed only humans. Machines can even perform better in some things than humans. Ability of the machines to demonstrate a high level of intelligence like humans is known as Artificial Intelligence (AI). The goal of this technological advancement could be to make life easier for humans. But before such technological advancement, there have been questions on the reality of the existence of a supreme power that is responsible for existence of life and universe. Now that machines can operate with intelligence accrued to human or even better, is there a need for a supreme power or do humans need to believe in a supreme being any longer? Studies have been conducted on the influence of AI on pastoral roles and on Christianity generally; but there is a little or no study on how pastors could affirm biblical metaphysics in the era of AI in Nigeria. Relying on transformational theory, the paper used a phenomenological design to interrogated the role of pastors in ensuring biblical metaphysics in this era of AI in Nigeria. The paper found that AI has the tendency of influencing how humans especially pastors, perceive reality. Therefore, it was concluded that pastors should understand AI and its functions; but maintain the teachings of the Bible and not replace the role of the Holy Spirit with AI. The paper recommended that pastors should update themselves with the current technological development, especially AI, in order to balance their roles as pastors.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Metaphysical Reality, Pastoral Counselors, Supreme Power, Technological Evolution

Introduction

The understanding and personal response to metaphysical questions is major factors that determine many other, if not all the aspects of human existence. Such aspects of existence include beliefs, worldview, relationships with others, personal dignity and esteem, attitude to work, integrity, and life's goal. Every human being directly or indirectly gives and answers to the questions. The questions according to Knight (2006) may include how did the universe originate and develop? This is a cosmological question. Another question is teleological, is there a purpose for the universe? There is also a theological question about the existence of God; does God exist? If he does, is he one or more? What are his attributes? If God exists and he is powerful, how is it that evil exists? Are there angels, Satan, and Holy Spirit? How do these relate to God? Another question that calls for answer is anthropological in nature. What is the relation between mind and body? What is humanity's moral status? Are humans born good, evil or morally neutral? To what extent are humans free and do they have free will, or are their thoughts and actions determined by their environment and inheritance? Another important question is ontological (nature of existence) which states, is basic reality in matter or physical energy (the world we can see), or is it found in spirit? Is it composed of one element (e.g. matter or spirit), or two (matter and spirit), or many? Is reality orderly and lawful in itself, or is it merely

orderable by theorists? Is it fixed and stable, or is change its central feature? Is the reality friendly, unfriendly, or neutral in regards to humanity?

The above metaphysical question and more are answered directly or indirectly, consciously or unconsciously and the answers given to them determine personal worldview which defines humans' thoughts, beliefs, and actions. Whatever position anyone takes in answering the questions reflects in their political social, religious, and educational practices and designs (Knight, 2006). Worldview has been defined by Sire (2004) as

A commitment, a fundamental orientation of the heart, that can be expressed as a story or a set of presumptions (assumptions which may be true, partially true or entirely false) which we hold (consciously or subconsciously, consistently or inconsistently) about the basic constitution of reality, and that provides the foundation on which we live and move and have our being (p. 17).

There are different factors that could influence people's answers to the metaphysical question to build personal worldview. The factors include family where one is born, upbringing, environment, education, personal experience which include exposure. One of the personal experience, education or exposure factors that could influence personal approach to metaphysical understanding and expression is technology especially Artificial Intelligence (AI) specifically in this age.

Adebiyi (2022), speaking on rise of atheism in Nigeria, argued that the Internet has contributed to the growth of atheism, which is one of the responses to metaphysical questions. According to him, when people could find answers to their questions outside of religion, the tendency is to claim that there is no God. With the emerging AI, there is possibility that atheism may increase in Nigeria. And according to Oduah (2018), "the effect of atheism will be terrible. It will lead to anarchy and chaos." This calls for the need to establish metaphysical reality as AI takes over human roles. Therefore, using phenomenology design which is a design in qualitative approach to research, this paper examines the role pastoral counselors could play in establishing metaphysical reality in this AI era.

Literature Review

Metaphysics is about the nature of reality (Fine, 2011). It is a branch of philosophy that deals with the questions on cosmology, theology, anthropology and ontology. In another way, metaphysics asks the questions such as: What is real? What is the meaning of change? Does the universe have design and purpose? Are children born evil or good? Do humans have free will? (Ozmon & Craver, 2003). According to Knight (2006), every human being assumes answers to these questions and their answers become the assumptions that determine their operations in daily lives; and there is no one who can escape from metaphysical decisions because they are bases of every human decision and behavior. They impact social, religious, education, political, economic and scientific beliefs and practices (Knight, 2006; Rennie, Sjostedt-Heughes & Morgan, 2023). Ozmon and Craver (2003), advised that people should be encouraged to shape their own intelligent views of metaphysics rather than uncritically accept the views handed down to them. Some of the factors that determine people's understanding and answers to metaphysical questions include personal experiences, culture, upbringing, education, religion, and technology. Considering these factors in the current era, technology, especially information space according to Belavkina, Lysenko, and Finochenko (2024) has become the major factors influencing all types of human activity. According to them, global "informatization" and digitalization affect bodily, mental and social constructs; affect the duration and quality of life and AI is a major tool in the global "informatization."

Artificial Intelligence (AI) according to Haenlein and Kaplan (2019) is "a system's ability to interpret external data correctly, to learn from such data, and to use those learnings to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation" (p. 1). Robinson (2018) presented AI as the ability of a digital computer, computer-controlled machine or robot to perform roles and activities that are commonly associated with intelligent beings like humans. This implies that the special ability endowed to humans and which differentiated

humans from other animals is being transferred to machines by humans themselves in order that the machines could take over and perform human responsibilities. Robinson (2018) stated that AI performs many smarter activities than natural intelligence. There are indications that the machines can learn from experience, adjust to new inputs and perform human-like task. They are also considered as completely human like and can perform things such as feeling, foreseeing, and making decisions (Mijwel, 2015).

Although the beginning of AI could be traced to as far back as 1942, it was established as academic discipline in the 1950s but remained an area of relative scientific obscurity and limited practical interest in computing power but has been in business environment and public conversation (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019; Robinson, 2018). The term artificial intelligence was first used by John McCarthy in an academic conference in the year 1957 and the applications were introduced during the period. Artificial intelligence had gone through many evolutionary processes built on the development of modern technology, hardware and software and the computer and information business models based on previous inventions such as the steam machines, the typewriter, the telephone, and electricity (Sinkovec & Jagodic, 2021). According to Sinkovec and Jagodic (2021), AI has been accepted by all the countries in the world and is present everywhere; in essence, it has come to stay. It has become increasingly prominent in education, with enormous potential to improve teaching and learning experience (Nurjanah, Salsabia, Azzahra, Rahayu, & Marlina, 2024). The various forms of AI include, neural networks, planning, robotics, machine learning, natural language processing, perception, knowledge, and cognitive system (Verma, Kaushal, Manugula, Ashok, & Monika, (2023).

Scholars have opined that AI has impact on human existence (Belavkina, Lysenko, & Finochenko, 2024; Du, 2024; Duggal, 2024; Krasadakis, 2023; Slimi, 2023; Tai, 2020). Some of the benefits include:

1. *Medical diagnosis:* AI is used to diagnose diseases and administer treatment in a reliable and safe system of health-care delivery. AI-based surgical procedures have been available for people to choose; it is observed that it completes surgical operation with more degree of precision and accuracy and less damage of the body.
2. *Assisted living:* Cyborgs (type of AI) visit elderly people who are alone in the developed world and assist with household chores. This allows elderly people can live better.
3. *Error reduction:* Error at work from human fatigue is being reduced through the use of AI. Since AI technology does not suffer from fatigue or emotional distraction. It saves error and can accomplish duty faster and more accurately.
4. *Revolutionize education:* AI has revolutionized education by personalizing teaching methods to suit individual student needs, providing prompt feedback, and automating administrative tasks. AI also assists in grading, assessment, development of curriculum. It influences learning experiences, facilitates acquisition of new knowledge and skills.

In the nearest future, AI will connect everything in human life holistically; human lives will be digitally enabled and be interconnected in a true Internet of Everything (IoE) manner. This will make AI systems to intelligently monitor every aspect of human lives including the infrastructure used by human. AI will fully be aware of how these things interact with each other and then make decision and take action on behalf of human that benefit society in a range of ways, in essence, everywhere humans go, the environments will be completely aware of them and will optimize the environment for them (Krasadakis, 2023).

In addition, AI will empower numerous automated systems to become fully autonomous in their operation and deliver value without the need for human intervention. This is already coming up with the evolution of self-driving cars. It will create knowledge that is not previously in existence which may be faster than humans can absorb and apply, thereby making AI surpass human intelligence and only AI able to use the new knowledge. Human challenges like food security, climate change, economic stability, poverty eradication, and disease eradication will be addressed by AI. However, AI according to Humble (2024) has become weaponized parallel to the nuclear arms that it has replaced automated weapons systems. The militarization

of AI has implications for global security and warfare (Marwala, 2023). Ai will become both sentient and malevolent towards humanity, and may unleash some form of war against humanity to either subdue or eradicate them (Cummings, 2017).

Biblical metaphysics is the systemic development of answers to the metaphysical questions based on hints and latent assumptions within the Bible. It reconciles traditional metaphysical inquiries with biblical teachings by focusing on the nature of God, creation, the relationship between God and his creation, and the ultimate purpose of human existence. The question of what is real has been an old age question because every human being struggles to and the question of existence and reality. To answer this question, Spiegel (2023) specified that the Bible speaks to metaphysical issues in the aspects of the nature of God, the cosmos, and the reality of a spiritual realm that transcends human observable physical domain.

The essence of this paper advocating for biblical metaphysics is an indication that there are different metaphysics just as mentioned by Benson (2010) that there are different metaphysical concepts. According to him biblical metaphysics must be about God the Creator. If there are different views about reality even before the evolution of AI, it is evident that there is possibility for biblical metaphysics to be eroded more than before. It is essential therefore, to examine how pastors, those who subscribe and hold to biblical metaphysics, understand the AI and its influence on the biblical metaphysics and the roles expected of them to establish biblical metaphysics.

Since metaphysics determines what reality is to individuals, biblical metaphysics is the conviction that God is the ultimate reality; he has been in existence before anything and will continue to exist, nothing exists without him. There are different realities to different individuals and one of such in this age is AI which has become everything to many people. Transformational theory according to Hiebert (2008), is a basic need of Christians to place people in the right mindset to imbibe right belief which is biblical especially when there are different alternatives. According to the theory, people have to belief in deity, virgin birth, and death and resurrection of Jesus Christ to be saved. This is a process that takes place inwardly but is revealed in the behavior of people. AI has the tendency to present alternative seemingly tangible things to people as the reality. Therefore, AI to be presented to people as a means to understand reality and not a reality on itself. Hiebert (2008) opined that the transformation process has three levels which are behavior, belief, and the worldview. AI is not to replace God in the life of people; it should be a tool to expose them to knowledge which could help build an appropriate worldview having God as the ultimate reality. This in turn will shape their belief and show in their behavior.

Methodology

Phenomenology design was adopted for this study. It is a design under qualitative research approach. Phenomenology is a research design in which principles or essence of a phenomenon is described (Creswell, 2007). It was an appropriate design for this study since the purpose was to describe the principles of establishing biblical metaphysics in this AI era. The population of the study comprised a class of pastors going through a postgraduate study in pastoral ministry, totaled 21. Among them was a female pastor. The age range of the pastors was 27–60. Interview guide was the instrument used for data collection and was conducted in their class where everyone had opportunity to give his/her response to the questions asked. The questions posted to them include, what understanding do you have about AI? What are the effects AI can have on humanity? Can there be influence on understanding of creation, purpose of the world, God, good and evil morality, and reality? What should be the roles of pastors? Responses were recorded using pen and paper and were analyzed thematically.

Findings

The analysis of the collected data generated three categories of findings with different themes under each. The three categories are: understanding of AI, problems from AI, and the role of pastors in AI era.

Understanding of AI

From the analysis of the collected data, the respondents have different understanding of what AI is about. While some do not have any knowledge of AI, one of them is undergoing different lectures on AI so as to make him understand AI, the use and the danger it poses. A good number of the respondents have some understanding of AI. According to them, AI is computer software that can do many things with a level of intelligence. In effort to describe it, a respondent indicated that AI is a system that goes into the cloud and bring together all information on a particular word or subject put into it. Some of the AI machines identified by the respondents are, Google, robots, robotic, self-driving car.

The respondents look at the name, "Artificial Intelligence" and argued that it is artificial according to the name and cannot be compared to natural intelligence given by God irrespective of what it does or able to do. One of the respondents tried to establish to superiority of natural intelligence gave an example of himself and her child. According to him, he wrote West African Examination Council many years ago and got two credits and one pass without any artificial intelligence; but his child wrote the same examination currently and had perfect scores in all the courses with the assistance of artificial intelligence. According to him, he could defend the courses he passed but his child could not defend anything from the perfect result. The respondents also argued that the evolution of different technological invention, especially AI is an indication of the authenticity of the Bible that says "knowledge shall increase." One of the respondents said, "The inventors of AI do not have correct worldview."

Problems from AI

The respondents identified different problems that may arise from the utilization of AI. It was emphasized that AI would have negative influence on humanity and human society. In the aspect of preaching, typing or telling a sermon title into AI machine brings about already prepared sermon that a pastor does not need to prepare again. Such sermon, according to the respondents may be entertaining but may not inspire anyone because it is not from experience.

The possibility of God being "cut off" from human activities was elaborated by the respondents. Since any question can be answered by AI and any concern can be settled by it, the need for God in human life may no longer be considered thereby leading to atheistic living. The knowledge of God may gradually be eroded from human mind and many become un-knowledgeable of God. The quest for connection with supreme God, which is spirituality, may not be part of human life again.

The Holy Bible used to be regarded as an authoritative word of God before this era; but with the coming of machines (AI) that can answer any question whether correctly or incorrectly, the authenticity of the Bible may be questioned. It was even assumed that the authenticity is already being questioned. The idea of Holy Spirit will be extinct. The information generated by AI sometime is not correct, humans will believe incorrect concept and live by it because true knowledge may not exist. This may lead the world to experience chaotic/catastrophic period because of falsehood.

The world is going into virtual living because of different AI machines; and virtual living is not real living. Human interpersonal relationship has been affected; humans are no longer having feeling and affection towards each other. It has become easy for one person to take the life of another. There is pleasure in fake living which has negatively influenced human characters and relationships. This, according to one of the respondents affirms the saying by Albert Einstein "I fear the day that technology will surpass our human interaction. The world will have a generation of idiots." People no longer need to remember anything or

think about anything because machines do all for them. The God's given potentials in humans will become redundant and humanity will degenerate. Children will become dull and morality will lose its essence. This will also affect human health negatively because they will not live active and relational life for which they were created.

Role of Pastors

When it comes to what the role of pastors should be in the era AI, the respondents opined that pastors should guard their heart as written in Proverbs 4:23, by having time with the study of the Bible. Pastors are to acknowledge and accept the existence of AI but should not allow themselves to be carried away by total dependence on it. They should always engage their God's given intelligence, studying, and meditating on positive information.

Pastors should create positive information and also send it to the cloud so that it could be made available to people. While there are errors in the cloud and AI brings them to people, biblical and salvific information should flood the cloud from pastors.

Pastors should teach members and young people about AI, letting them know the benefits and dangers and the way to positively utilize the machines because of this, pastors should not pretend as if nothing of such is in existence. Pastors are to understand the ethical guidance to AI and let their members have the knowledge as well.

Any opportunity opened to pastors should be used to present balanced gospel in the context of the reality of AI. Pastors should not fail to present and affirm God as the Creator and Sustainer of life. He is above all and He is the source of true knowledge. The Holy Bible is God's word to make human wise.

Christian churches, speaking of local congregations, are embracing digitalization of churches. If care is not taken, members are being encouraged to be digital dependence and thereby having their minds opened for taking over by AI. Therefore, there may be a need to de-digitalize of churches and embrace the old-time religion.

Discussion of Findings

The low level of awareness of AI by the respondents indicated the need for pastors to be sensitive to the environment and the phenomena going on in the society to enable relevant ministry. The respondents were not aware of extent which AI has reached in influencing humanity; for instance, Robot has led out in church service in Germany (check <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lwF3Xp1U18c>). Courcy (2022) emphasized that pastors are to be aware of events in their environment. Aragba-Akpore (September 22, 2024), opined that human affairs are increasingly being run on artificial intelligence. He indicated that in June 2024, a church congregation of no fewer than 300 people held service that was conducted by a robotic tool powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Different opportunities and challenges were identified with the existence of AI and pastoral ministry. The challenges ranged from God and Holy Spirit being cut off from human knowledge and the Bible become irrelevant, error messages that people imbibe, and belittling the importance of the Bible in human life. While some have encouraged the use of AI in the ministry (Nicholson, 2023; Robinson, 2018; Tithely, 2023) for editing, brainstorming ideas, translation assistance, and research assistance, many have written about the limitation it may bring to the ministry (Alford, 2024; Christianity Today, 2023; Jambrek, 2024; Siyaya, 2017). Pastors are to take caution in the use of AI without substituting it for the Holy Spirit or the Bible.

Conclusion

The evolution of AI has brought a change in every human endeavor and it has come to stay with no one knowing how far it will reach. Due to the different roles AI machines can perform, the acceptance of biblical

metaphysics may be challenged by many individuals. The belief about God being the ultimate reality according to the Bible could be doubted. Both the belief, behavior and worldview of people are to be issues of concern to pastors since worldview determines what ultimate reality is to individuals. AI should be considered as means to knowledge about reality and not reality in itself. Therefore, since pastors teach biblical truth and metaphysical belief is the basic one, the study concluded that pastors have deep understanding of AI in its various forms. They are to teach the biblical truth about God being the ultimate reality using AI as tools for teaching.

Recommendations

1. Pastors should get updated with the technological tools to have understanding of how they work. They should not only be living in the old ways of doing things.
2. Pastors should talk about AI, making members to understand both the benefits and hazards in it.
3. Pastors should make use of AI devices by writing and posting messages that emphasize biblical metaphysical teachings.
4. In the usage of AI, pastors should maintain balance of not placing it above human beings created by God.
5. Pastors should affirm biblical metaphysics and teach it always using every medium possible including AI devices.

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